

Accepted manuscript

Title: Calcium and strontium phytate particles as a potential drug delivery system for prolonged release of risedronate

Authors: Mariusz Sandomierski, Marcel Jakubowski, Maria Ratajczak, Tomasz Buchwald, Robert E. Przekop, Łukasz Majchrzycki, Adam Voelkel

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2023.104176>

Published in: Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology

Please cite this article as: M. Sandomierski, M. Jakubowski, M. Ratajczak, T. Buchwald, R.E. Przekop, Ł. Majchrzycki, A. Voelkel, Calcium and strontium phytate particles as a potential drug delivery system for prolonged release of risedronate, Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology, 80, (2023) 104176.

This is a PDF file of an unedited manuscript that has been accepted for publication. The accepted manuscript was published on the Zenodo database after the expiry of the embargo period and with the consent of Elsevier.

Calcium and strontium phytate particles as a potential drug delivery system for prolonged release of risedronate

Mariusz Sandomierski^{*1}, Marcel Jakubowski¹, Maria Ratajczak², Tomasz Buchwald³,

Robert E. Przekop⁴, Łukasz Majchrzycki⁴, Adam Voelkel¹

¹ Institute of Chemical Technology and Engineering, Poznan University of Technology, ul. Berdychowo 4, 60-965 Poznań, Poland

² Institute of Building Engineering, Poznan University of Technology, ul. Piotrowo 5, 60-965 Poznań, Poland

³ Institute of Materials Research and Quantum Engineering, Poznań University of Technology, Piotrowo 3, 60-965 Poznań, Poland

⁴ Centre for Advanced Technologies, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, ul. Uniwersytetu Poznańskiego 10, 61-614 Poznań, Poland

*e-mail: mariusz.sandomierski@put.poznan.pl

Abstract

Risedronate is a bisphosphonate drug. It is a group of drugs that is mainly used to treat osteoporosis. Their biggest disadvantages are very poor bioavailability and short half-life in plasma. The use of modern drug carriers may be an attempt to solve this problem. In this work, for the first time, a carrier based on calcium and strontium phytate particles was prepared. These metals were selected because they are non-toxic and have positive effect in the treatment of osteoporosis. The obtained materials were characterized using many research techniques (SEM, EDS, Zeta potential, FT-IR, Raman, TGA). The conducted research confirms successful synthesis of calcium and strontium phytate particles and effective retention of the drug on the surface of prepared phytates. The research carried out shows how the used cation influence sorption and desorption properties. Drug desorption profiles shows that RSD is released gradually, which may favorably affect its bioavailability.

Keywords: Phytate, risedronate, drug carriers, controlled release, osteoporosis

1. Introduction

Bisphosphonates (BPs) are drugs that bind with calcium ions and are used to treat bone-related diseases such as osteoporosis and Paget's disease. Some studies also show that some bisphosphonates have potent anti-cancer effects [1–3]. Additionally, the bisphosphonates used today can be divided into two classes: those that have a nitrogen atom in their structure or those that do not [4]. Bisphosphonates are analogs of pyrophosphate (P-O-P), which contain a carbon atom (P-C-P) instead of an oxygen atom between the phosphorus atoms. Bisphosphonates with this structure, having two phosphorus atoms attached to one carbon atom, are called geminal bisphosphonates, and only these have a strong effect on the skeleton. Due to this structure, they are resistant to many factors, such as temperature or enzymatic hydrolysis [5,6]. BPs can effectively bind to Ca^{2+} ions and induce osteoclast apoptosis, which results in the inhibition of bone resorption [7]. Bisphosphonates have two routes of administration, which differ in their side effects. Side effects after oral administration of the drug are mainly related to the digestive system. Some of these include, for example, inflammation of the esophagus, gastritis, and heartburn or nausea [8,9]. On the other hand, intravenous administration of the drug may cause, for example, fever, muscle, joint pain, or vomiting. Some BPs can cause more serious adverse reactions. These include acute or chronic renal failure, electrolyte disturbances (e.g., hypocalcemia), and many others [10]. Another problem during therapy with this group of drugs is their poor bioavailability. This is due to very poor absorption from the gastrointestinal tract (about 0.7% for nitrogen-containing BPs) when administered orally. During intravenous therapy, it is caused by the fact that immediately after administration, about 50% is bound to the bones, and the remaining 50% unchanged is removed by the kidneys [11,12].

One potential solution to the problems mentioned above is the use of a drug delivery system (DDS). The use of DDS has been shown to improve bioavailability. As carriers used in the creation of such systems, mainly nanoparticles are used. The prepared carrier should be biocompatible and should release the drug under the influence of body fluids [13,14]. Phytic acid is a natural compound found in plants such as soybeans and corn, the function of which is to store phosphorus [15]. This compound contains six phosphate groups in its structure, which makes it highly capable of binding ions such as Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+} . This substance is often used to create biocompatible coatings on titanium implants [16]. Some studies also show that, like bisphosphonates, it can inhibit the resorption of hydroxyapatite [17]. In our previous work, we proved that BPs interact strongly with Ca^{2+} cations [18]. In this paper, we would like to propose risedronate (RSD) delivery system based on calcium and strontium phytate particles. These ions have been selected because they are biocompatible and have the ability to increase osteoblast proliferation [19,20]. The prepared materials will be characterized using a variety of research techniques to investigate the size, morphology, and effective drug retention. The study will also investigate the effect of the cation on the amount of drug retained and its effect on the RSD release profile from the carrier. As mentioned earlier, it is also possible to synthesize this material on a titanium implant, which would allow the release of drugs for osteoporosis from its surface. The scheme of research conducted in this work is presented in Fig.1.

Figure 1. The scheme of the research presented in this work.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Materials

The phytic acid sodium salt, calcium nitrate tetrahydrate, strontium chloride hexahydrate, sodium risedronate (RSD), tris (hydroxymethyl) aminomethane (TRIS), (99.8%), sodium chloride (99%), sodium bicarbonate (99%), sodium sulfate (99%), potassium phosphate dibasic trihydrate (99%), potassium chloride (99%) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Hydrochloric acid (36-38%) was obtained from Avantor. The materials were used without further purification.

2.2 Carrier particles preparation

Calcium and strontium phytate particles were prepared using the simple precipitation method. The ion ratio used during the synthesis (6 Me^{2+} to 1 phytate anion) was taken from a paper published by Pechrova et al. [21]. First, salt solutions were prepared by mixing appropriate amount of calcium nitrate or strontium chloride with 20 ml of water to obtain 0.21M solutions. The pH of both solutions was adjusted to 8. Next, 40 ml of 0.034M sodium phytate solution was prepared, and its pH was also adjusted to 8. The pH during the synthesis was adjusted with 0.1M NaOH or HCl solutions. The salt solutions were placed on a magnetic stirrer, and equal volumes of the prepared solutions were mixed while continuously stirring. A white precipitate formed immediately after the solutions were mixed. Both mixtures were mixed for 1 hour at room temperature. The precipitate was then collected by centrifugation, washed several times with distilled water, and dried at 60°C. Obtained calcium phytate and strontium phytate particles were named Ca-PHYT and Sr-PHYT, respectively.

2.3 Drug loading

Drug sorption was initiated by introducing 30 mg of Ca-PHYT or Sr-PHYT samples into Eppendorf tubes. Each tube was filled with 1.5ml of sodium risedronate solution with a concentration of 0.2 mg/ml (sodium risedronate solution was prepared by dissolving it in 0.1M TRIS-HCl buffer pH 7.4). Next, samples were placed on a laboratory rotator mixer (50 rpm). Drug sorption measurements were carried out after 1, 2, 3, and 7 days. Before each measurement samples were centrifuged (5min 4500 rpm) before UV-VIS analysis. Six repetitions were made for each material.

After the drug loading process samples were named Ca-PHYT-RSD and Sr-PHYT-RSD.

2.4 Drug Release

The drug release process was carried out as follows. The prepared carriers after drug sorption were placed in 1.5 ml of simulated body fluids (SBF). The composition of SBF is shown in Table 1. The amount of drug release was checked every hour up to 24 hours and measured by UV-VIS spectroscopy. Each time, the samples were centrifuged (4500rpm, 5min), and a new aliquot of SBF was added to them. The temperature of the experiment was 36.6°C to simulate the temperature of the human body. Three repetitions were made for both materials.

Table 1. Composition of the SBF used in this work (1000 ml of the SBF).

Order	Reagent	Amount
1.	NaCl	8.035 g
2.	NaHCO ₃	0.355 g
3.	KCl	0.225 g
4.	K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	0.231 g
5.	Na ₂ SO ₄	0.072 g
6.	TRIS	0.6112 g
7.	HCl	0-5 ml

2.5 .UV-VIS Spectroscopy

UV-VIS spectroscopy was used to study the amount of sodium risedronate retained on the carrier surface and during the study of its release. The tests were carried out using the UV-2600 apparatus (Shimadzu, Japan). Measurements were made in the range of 230-305 nm (λ max=262nm).

2.6. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) / Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS)

Scanning electron microscopy images were taken with the VEGA SEM (TESCAN, Czech Republic). The SEM device was equipped with an EDS analyzer (Bruker, UK). EDS was used to analyze the composition of elements on the surface of the prepared samples. The final content of a given element was obtained by taking the average of ten measurements at different spots.

2.7. Zeta potential

Zeta potentials of the materials were determined with the use of a Zetasizer Nano ZS apparatus (Malvern Instruments Ltd., United Kingdom). The measurements were carried out at pH 7. The tested material (1 mg/ml) was sonicated in an ultrasonic bath in distilled water for 3 minutes. Five repetitions were made for each material.

2.8. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

FT-IR analysis was performed using a Vertex70 spectrometer (Bruker Optics, Germany). The tests were performed using the ATR crystal with a single diamond reflection. The spectral range of the research was in the range of 4000 cm^{-1} – 600 cm^{-1} and with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . During one examination, 32 scans were performed to accumulate the signal.

2.9. Raman Spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy analysis was conducted using inVia Raman system (Renishaw plc, United Kingdom). Raman spectra was recorded in the range of 200 cm^{-1} to 3200 cm^{-1} using 785 nm laser. The laser beam was focused use of 50x lens ensuring spatial resolution about $1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The distribution of RSD in Ca-PHYT and Sr-PHYT was

presented using the Raman mapping. Raman maps were collected on 200 μm x 200 μm surface with 10 μm step measurement.

2.10. Thermogravimetric analysis

Thermogravimetry (TG) was performed using a NETZSCH 209 F1 Libra gravimetric analyzer (Selb, Germany). Samples of 2 ± 0.2 mg were placed in Al_2O_3 crucibles. Measurements were conducted under nitrogen (flow of 20 mL/min) in the range of 30–1000°C and a 10°C/min heating rate.

2.11. Kinetic models

The drug release profile can be assessed using several mathematical models. The releasing profiles in this work were investigated with the use of two models [22]. The obtained data were fitted using zero-order, and first-order models [22].

Zero-order equation:

$$Q_t = Q_0 + K_0t$$

where Q_t is the amount of drug dissolved in time t , Q_0 is the initial amount of drug in the solution and K_0 is the zero-order release constant expressed in units of concentration/time.

First-order equation:

$$\log C = \log C_0 - K_t / 2.303$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration of drug and K is first-order constant.

3. Results and Discussion

In the images taken with SEM (Fig 2), we can see that the obtained Ca-PHYT and Sr-PHYT particles do not differ from each other. We can also see that the materials are similar to those obtained earlier by Ganesan et al. [23]. Furthermore, after the sorption process of the drug, no significant differences between the obtained

materials are visible. The particles in all materials are agglomerated, but this is due to the fact that they were subjected to a drying process before the SEM analysis [23]. The fact that no new crystalline forms are visible after the sorption process suggests that the drug was retained only on the surface of the material and not precipitated. The photos also show that the particles obtained are very small in size (most likely they are nanoparticles).

Figure 2. Sem images of prepared materials.

To determine how particles of carriers and carriers with the drug behave in a solution with a pH close to human body fluids, the zeta potential was measured (Table 2.). A sample is electrokinetically stable when the zeta potential absolute value is above 30

[24]. As can be seen, the values for all materials are similar and are below -35 mV. This proves that the suspension is electrostatically stabilized and therefore the carrier suspension should not tend to agglomerate [25].

Table 2. Zeta potential of prepared materials.

	Zeta potential (mV)
Ca-PHYT	-37.9 ± 0.8
Ca-PHYT-RSD	-38.2 ± 1.1
Sr-PHYT	-37.0 ± 1.0
Sr-PHYT-RSD	-38.4 ± 0.9

The scanning electron microscope was also equipped with an EDS device, it was used to determine the content of ions in the prepared materials and also to check the ratio of Ca^{2+} and Sr^{2+} ions to phosphorus (Me^{2+}/P) in the prepared materials. These results are presented in Table 3. As we can see, this ratio is close to 1:1 which is consistent with the literature reports on this subject [26]. Differences between all materials are not statistically significant.

Table 3. The amount of metals and the molar ratio of Me^{2+}/P in the prepared materials (atomic %).

	$\text{Me}^{2+}(\%)$	P(%)	Me^{2+}/P (molar)
Ca-PHYT	14.8 ± 4.3	16.3 ± 4.0	1:1.10
Ca-PHYT-RSD	16.4 ± 4.0	17.9 ± 4.7	1:1.08
Sr-PHYT	14.0 ± 2.1	14.8 ± 1.5	1:1.05
Sr-PHYT-RSD	14.9 ± 2.6	15.3 ± 2.1	1:1.02

FT-IR spectroscopy is one of the techniques that has been used to confirm effective drug retention on the carrier surface. The spectrum obtained after drug sorption has additional bands that were absent before the sorption process (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. FT-IR spectroscopy measurements before and after drug sorption.

In all samples, a wide band between the wavenumber 3630-2750 cm^{-1} and a sharp band at the wavenumber of 1640 cm^{-1} can be observed. These bands are assigned to the vibrations of the O-H bond and residual water on the material, respectively. All spectra also have bands that can be attributed to the vibration of the C-O bond, these are bands at a wavenumber of around 793 cm^{-1} , 842 cm^{-1} , and 1396 cm^{-1} . There are also bands belonging to the P-O bond vibration at wavenumber around 980 cm^{-1} and 1080 cm^{-1} [15,21,27]. It is also worth emphasizing that all bands for strontium phytate are slightly shifted towards lower wavenumber values in relation to calcium phytate. According to the literature, it means that interactions between phosphate groups from phytic acid and divalent ions are stronger for calcium than strontium [26]. New bands visible after the sorption stage in the range of 1600 cm^{-1} – 1450 cm^{-1} of the drug can be attributed to the stretching vibrations of the C=C and C=N bonds [28,29]. The

band at 1470 cm^{-1} occurs at the same wavenumber as the band in pure drug (Figure 4.). The second band is shifted, but this phenomenon has occurred before, for example, for montmorillonite and zeolites [30,31]. These bands most likely come from the pyridinium ring present in the risedronate structure.

Figure 4. FT-IR spectrum for the risedronate.

The prepared materials were also characterized using Raman spectroscopy. The obtained spectra (Fig. 5), show bands which are mainly assigned to the vibration of the phosphate groups in the phytic acid molecule. For example, the bands at 1002 cm^{-1} , 1090 cm^{-1} , 1145 cm^{-1} and 1380 cm^{-1} can be assigned to O-P-O or P=O deformation vibrations. Some bands also belong to the vibrations of the bonds that occur between carbon or between carbon and oxygen atoms. These are for example bands at 546 cm^{-1} or 1296 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to deformation vibrations of C-C and stretching vibrations of C-O and C-C bonds respectively [32,33]. After the sorption step, an additional band appears at the wavelength of 1470 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to the stretching vibration of the pyridinium ring originating from the drug molecule [34]. This band is shifted relative to the pure drug spectrum (Figure 6). The

lack of other bands is most likely because the drug bands are in the same range as the phytate bands. We also mapped the surface of the prepared carriers to verify that the drug was uniformly distributed over the entire surface. RSD is retained evenly on both materials, with no obvious medicine agglomerates, which means that always the same amount of drug will be released from the same amount of carrier (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Raman spectra of carriers before and after drug sorption (top) and Raman maps for the ratio of the 1470 cm⁻¹ band intensity (RSD) to the 1380 cm⁻¹ band intensity (Ca-PHYT, Sr-PHYT) recorded on the surface of Ca-PHYT, Sr-PHYT, Ca-PHYT-RSD, and Sr-PHYT-RSD (middle and bottom).

Figure 6. Raman spectra of risedronate.

The prepared carriers were also characterized using thermal techniques (TGA / DTG), the results are presented in Fig. 7. Thermal degradation of all samples is similar and in each case takes place in 4 stages. The first weight loss beginning at about 40°C is related to the loss of physically adsorbed water molecules remaining in the material. The second weight loss starting at 220°C is associated with the removal of OH groups from acidic phosphate groups [35]. 3rd effects weight loss starts at 600°C and is due to the full carbonization of the samples [36]. The presence of Ca and Sr leads potentially to the formation of carbonates, phosphates and pyrophosphates, the decomposition of which is visible at temperatures above 870°C in the last stage of the decomposition process [37–39]. As can be seen, the drug-treated materials show a greater weight loss, which may be due to the fact that they have similar functional groups which degrade at the same temperature.

Figure 7. TGA curves before and after drug sorption (top left), DTG curve of RSD (top right), and DTG curves before and after RSD sorption (bottom).

The DTG curves (Fig. 7) confirm the observations that the thermal decomposition of phytates occurs in 4 steps. There are also some differences in the curves between samples that contain RSD and those that do not. This is another technique that confirms effective drug retention. In both materials after drug sorption, we can notice a shift of the peak in the second stage of degradation towards lower temperature values. This may be due to the dehydroxylation at a lower temperature of the alcoholic OH group derived from the RSD structure. Another difference is the wider peaks above 600 degrees that may be related to the carbonization of the pyridinium ring [36]. These observations are confirmed by the DTG analysis of pure risedronate (Fig. 7).

Drug sorption studies performed using UV-VIS spectroscopy showed that both materials are capable of retaining risedronate on their surface. As we can see in Figure 8, calcium phytate retained approximately 0.216 mg and strontium phytate 0.162 mg. Relating these results to the amount of drug that was used during sorption, Ca-PHYT retained 71.9 % of drug, and Sr-PHYT-RSD retained 53.7 % of drug. The fact that calcium ion-containing material retained more drug is due to the fact that risedronate interacts more with these ions than with strontium ions. This is in line with the literature reports on the subject [40]. The drug is retained on the surface of the carriers most likely by coordination interactions. This is because bisphosphonates form such bonds with divalent ions [41,42]. Of course, it can partially connect also through hydrogen bonds, but they are less stable due to which coordination interactions will prevail. The mechanism of bisphosphonate retention on the surface of the presented carriers is most likely similar to their sorption on the surface of apatites [29,43]. It can be considered that apatites are somewhat similar to phytates due to which these interactions will be very similar. It has already been proven in the literature that bisphosphonates interact mainly by coordination, and hydrogen bonds probably occur only between the pyridine ring and the surface of the apatite [44].

Figure 8. Drug sorption on the prepared materials after 7 days.

Drug release studies show (Fig. 9b) that large amounts of retained RSD are released, 0.180 mg (83%) and 0.161 mg (100%) for Ca-PHYT-RSD and Sr-PHYT-RSD respectively. We can also see that in both cases the release is slowed down. This is advantageous as it is likely to increase the bioavailability of the active ingredient. We can also see that the material containing strontium releases the drug more quickly. This is again related to the fact that bisphosphonates interact more strongly with calcium ions than strontium [36]. At the twelfth hour, the amount of drug released from calcium phytate exceeds the amount of drug released from strontium phytate, but this is not due to the accelerated release from Ca-PHYT-RSD, but because the drug runs out in Sr-PHYT-RSD. As can be seen in Figure 9 b Ca-PHYT-RSD did not release all the drug. Most likely, the drug is released further, but the doses are so small that it was not possible to measure them using the apparatus

used. Analyzing the amount of released drug in percent (%) also shows that in the initial stages the drug is released faster from Sr-PHYT-RSD.

Figure 9. Total release of risedronate from Ca-PHYT and Sr-PHYT. Cumulative drug released in milligrams (a). Cumulative amount of drug released in relation to the amount of drug retained, expressed in % (b).

The amount of drug released at each step was calculated and shown in Table 4. As can be seen in the first six hours (initial rates), Sr-PHYT-RSD ($21.8 \mu\text{g} / \text{h}$) releases more drug than Ca-PHYT-RSD ($18.4 \mu\text{g} / \text{h}$). In the remaining stages, larger doses are released from the Ca-PHYT-RSD.

Table 4. The average amount of drug released over a given time interval ($\mu\text{g} / \text{hour}$) and kinetic parameters of drug release for the tested materials.

	Ca-PHYT-RSD	Sr-PHYT-RSD
0-6 hours	18.4 $\mu\text{g} / \text{h}$	21.8 $\mu\text{g} / \text{h}$
7-12 hours	6.7 $\mu\text{g} / \text{h}$	3.2 $\mu\text{g} / \text{h}$
12 – 18 hours	3.9 $\mu\text{g} / \text{h}$	1.6 $\mu\text{g} / \text{h}$
Zero-order model [R^2] 0-6 hours	0.985	0.912
Zero-order model [R^2] 0-24 hours	0.855	0.706
First-order model [R^2] 0-6 hours	0.998	0.983
First-order model [R^2] 0-24 hours	0.968	0.986

Maintaining a desired value of drug at the site of action is the main criteria of controlled release systems. The kinetic parameters for release of risedronate including the correlation coefficient values (R^2) are presented in Table 4. It was concluded that the best results were observed for first-order model with R^2 ranging from 0.968 to 0.998, which may suggest the controlled drug release. Hence we can assume, that the drug release profile of risedronate from both carriers was based on its concentration [22]. Over all, the release studies show that the phytate carriers are suitable for sustained delivery of risedronate.

The sorption and drug release studies have shown that the cation used to synthesize phytates has an impact on the retention and release profile of the drug. Additionally,

the carrier prepared by our group is composed of natural biocompatible substances. Thanks to this, once the drug is released, the carrier can biodegrade in the body, which makes it possible to administer it by intravenous injections.

Conclusions

In the presented work we synthesized calcium and strontium phytate particles. They were used for the first time as a drug carriers for the bisphosphonate drug sodium risedronate. Performed analysis (FT-IR, Raman, Thermogravimetric analysis) were able to confirm successful drug sorption on the surface of prepared materials. Raman mapping shows that drug is distributed almost equally on the entire surface of the synthesized phytates. Material with Ca^{2+} ions was able to retain higher amounts of drug than material with Sr^{2+} cations. Drug release study shows that both prepared carriers are able to successfully release RSD from their surface, however drug is released more gradually from calcium phytate material.

Acknowledgements

This paper was produced with financial support from the Polish National Science Centre (grant number UMO-2020/39/B/ST5/00320).

Mariusz Sandomierski was supported by the Foundation for Polish Sciences (FNP).

Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

References

- [1] M.J. Rogers, J. Mönkkönen, M.A. Munoz, Molecular mechanisms of action of bisphosphonates and new insights into their effects outside the skeleton, *Bone*. 139 (2020) 115493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bone.2020.115493>.
- [2] I.R. Reid, D.J. Hosking, Bisphosphonates in Paget's disease, *Bone*. 49 (2011) 89–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bone.2010.09.002>.
- [3] N.M. La-Beck, X. Liu, H. Shmeeda, C. Shudde, A.A. Gabizon, Repurposing amino-bisphosphonates by liposome formulation for a new role in cancer treatment, *Semin. Cancer Biol.* 68 (2021) 175–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semcancer.2019.12.001>.

- [4] C.-H. Huang, S.B. Gabelli, E. Oldfield, L.M. Amzel, Binding of nitrogen-containing bisphosphonates (N-BPs) to the Trypanosoma cruzi farnesyl diphosphate synthase homodimer, *Proteins*. 78 (2010) 888–899. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.22614>.
- [5] K. Suzuki, S. Takeyama, S. Murakami, M. Nagaoka, M. Chiba, K. Igarashi, H. Shinoda, Structure-Dependent Effects of Bisphosphonates on Inflammatory Responses in Cultured Neonatal Mouse Calvaria, *Antioxid. Basel Switz.* 9 (2020) E503. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox9060503>.
- [6] A. Kuźnik, A. Październiok-Holewa, P. Jewula, N. Kuźnik, Bisphosphonates-much more than only drugs for bone diseases, *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 866 (2020) 172773. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2019.172773>.
- [7] M.T. Drake, B.L. Clarke, S. Khosla, Bisphosphonates: Mechanism of Action and Role in Clinical Practice, *Mayo Clin. Proc. Mayo Clin.* 83 (2008) 1032–1045.
- [8] C. Orozco, N.M. Maalouf, Safety of Bisphosphonates, *Rheum. Dis. Clin.* 38 (2012) 681–705. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rdc.2012.09.001>.
- [9] E.V. Giger, B. Castagner, J.-C. Leroux, Biomedical applications of bisphosphonates, *J. Control. Release Off. J. Control. Release Soc.* 167 (2013) 175–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2013.01.032>.
- [10] T. Tanvetyanon, P.J. Stiff, Management of the adverse effects associated with intravenous bisphosphonates, *Ann. Oncol. Off. J. Eur. Soc. Med. Oncol.* 17 (2006) 897–907. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annonc/mdj105>.
- [11] A.P. Soares, R.F. do Espírito Santo, S.R.P. Line, M. das G.F. Pinto, P. de M. Santos, M.B.P. Toralles, A.R. do Espírito Santo, Bisphosphonates: Pharmacokinetics, bioavailability, mechanisms of action, clinical applications in children, and effects on tooth development, *Environ. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 42 (2016) 212–217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etap.2016.01.015>.
- [12] S. Cremers, M.T. Drake, F.H. Ebetino, J.P. Bilezikian, R.G.G. Russell, Pharmacology of bisphosphonates, *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* 85 (2019) 1052–1062. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bcp.13867>.
- [13] S. Sur, A. Rathore, V. Dave, K.R. Reddy, R.S. Chouhan, V. Sadhu, Recent developments in functionalized polymer nanoparticles for efficient drug delivery system, *Nano-Struct. Nano-Objects.* 20 (2019) 100397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoso.2019.100397>.
- [14] K. Manjunath, V. Venkateswarlu, Pharmacokinetics, tissue distribution and bioavailability of clozapine solid lipid nanoparticles after intravenous and intraduodenal administration, *J. Control. Release Off. J. Control. Release Soc.* 107 (2005) 215–228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2005.06.006>.
- [15] F. Barahuie, D. Dorniani, B. Saifullah, S. Gothai, M.Z. Hussein, A.K. Pandurangan, P. Arulselvan, M.E. Norhaizan, Sustained release of anticancer agent phytic acid from its chitosan-coated magnetic nanoparticles for drug-delivery system, *Int. J. Nanomedicine.* 12 (2017) 2361–2372. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S126245>.
- [16] Q. Wang, C. Ding, Y. Zhou, J. Luo, J. Li, Universal and biocompatible hydroxyapatite coating induced by phytic acid-metal complex multilayer, *Colloids Surf. B Biointerfaces.* 169 (2018) 478–485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfb.2018.05.057>.
- [17] P. Sanchis, Á.-A. López-González, A. Costa-Bauzá, C. Busquets-Cortés, P. Riutord, P. Calvo, F. Grases, Understanding the Protective Effect of Phytate in Bone Decalcification Related-Diseases, *Nutrients.* 13 (2021) 2859. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13082859>.

- [18] M. Sandomierski, M. Zielińska, A. Voelkel, Calcium zeolites as intelligent carriers in controlled release of bisphosphonates, *Int. J. Pharm.* 578 (2020) 119117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2020.119117>.
- [19] D. Gregurec, N. Politakos, L. Yate, S.E. Moya, Strontium confinement in polyacrylic acid brushes: a soft nanoarchitectonics approach for the design of titania coatings with enhanced osseointegration, *Mol. Syst. Des. Eng.* 4 (2019) 421–430. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8ME00089A>.
- [20] Sunarso, A. Tsuchiya, R. Toita, K. Tsuru, K. Ishikawa, Impact of surface functionalization with phosphate and calcium on the biological performance of Ti-6Al-4V, *Mater. Lett.* 304 (2021) 130716. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2021.130716>.
- [21] Z. Pechrova, V. Lobaz, M. Konefał, R. Konefał, M. Hruby, Colloidal probe based on iron(III)-doped calcium phytate nanoparticles for ³¹P NMR monitoring of bacterial siderophores, *Colloid Interface Sci. Commun.* 42 (2021) 100427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colcom.2021.100427>.
- [22] S.M. Sreedharan, R. Singh, Ciprofloxacin Functionalized Biogenic Gold Nanoflowers as Nanoantibiotics Against Pathogenic Bacterial Strains, *Int. J. Nanomedicine.* 14 (2019) 9905–9916. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S224488>.
- [23] K. Ganesan, M. Eppele, Calcium phosphate nanoparticles as nuclei for the preparation of colloidal calcium phytate, *New J. Chem.* 32 (2008) 1326–1330. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B803903H>.
- [24] M. Stanis, Ł. Klapiszewski, D. Moszyński, B.J. Stanis, T. Jesionowski, Evaluation of cilazapril release profiles with the use of lignin-based spherical particles, *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol.* 75 (2022) 103636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2022.103636>.
- [25] S. Kamble, S. Agrawal, S. Cherumukil, V. Sharma, R.V. Jasra, P. Munshi, Revisiting Zeta Potential, the Key Feature of Interfacial Phenomena, with Applications and Recent Advancements, *ChemistrySelect.* 7 (2022) e202103084. <https://doi.org/10.1002/slct.202103084>.
- [26] J. Torres, S. Domínguez, M.F. Cerdá, G. Obal, A. Mederos, R.F. Irvine, A. Díaz, C. Kremer, Solution behaviour of myo-inositol hexakisphosphate in the presence of multivalent cations. Prediction of a neutral pentamagnesium species under cytosolic/nuclear conditions, *J. Inorg. Biochem.* 99 (2005) 828–840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinorgbio.2004.12.011>.
- [27] Z. He, C.W. Honeycutt, T. Zhang, P.M. Bertsch, Preparation and FT-IR characterization of metal phytate compounds, *J. Environ. Qual.* 35 (2006) 1319–1328. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2006.0008>.
- [28] D.K. Khajuria, R. Razdan, D.R. Mahapatra, Development, in vitro and in vivo characterization of zoledronic acid functionalized hydroxyapatite nanoparticle based formulation for treatment of osteoporosis in animal model, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci. Off. J. Eur. Fed. Pharm. Sci.* 66 (2015) 173–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2014.10.015>.
- [29] F. Errassifi, S. Sarda, A. Barroug, A. Legrouri, H. Sfihi, C. Rey, Infrared, Raman and NMR investigations of risedronate adsorption on nanocrystalline apatites, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 420 (2014) 101–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2014.01.017>.
- [30] M. Sandomierski, M. Zielińska, A. Voelkel, Calcium zeolites as intelligent carriers in controlled release of bisphosphonates, *Int. J. Pharm.* 578 (2020) 119117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2020.119117>.

- [31] M. Sandomierski, M. Zielińska, K. Adamska, A. Patalas, A. Voelkel, Calcium montmorillonite as a potential carrier in the release of bisphosphonates, *New J. Chem.* 46 (2022) 3401–3408. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1NJ04268H>.
- [32] H. Yang, Y. Yang, Y. Yang, H. Liu, Z. Zhang, G. Shen, R. Yu, Formation of inositol hexaphosphate monolayers at the copper surface from a Na-salt of phytic acid solution studied by in situ surface enhanced Raman scattering spectroscopy, Raman mapping and polarization measurement, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 548 (2005) 159–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2005.05.061>.
- [33] C. Li, X. Guo, S. Shen, P. Song, T. Xu, Y. Wen, H.-F. Yang, Adsorption and corrosion inhibition of phytic acid calcium on the copper surface in 3wt% NaCl solution, *Corros. Sci.* 83 (2014) 147–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2014.02.001>.
- [34] Y. Gao, L. Chen, X. Dai, R. Song, B. Wang, Z. Wang, A strong charge-transfer effect in surface-enhanced Raman scattering induced by valence electrons of actinide elements, *RSC Adv.* 5 (2015) 32198–32204. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5RA03408F>.
- [35] H.-J. de Jager, L.C. Prinsloo, The dehydration of phosphates monitored by DSC/TGA and in situ Raman spectroscopy, *Thermochim. Acta.* 376 (2001) 187–196. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6031\(01\)00582-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6031(01)00582-2).
- [36] G. Vlase, P. Albu, S.C. Doca, M. Mateescu, T. Vlase, The kinetic study of the thermally induced degradation and an evaluation of the drug–excipient interactions performed for a new-generation bisphosphonate—risedronate, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 134 (2018) 721–730. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-018-7216-9>.
- [37] R.E. Przekop, P. Marciniak, B. Sztorch, A. Czapik, M. Stodolny, A. Martyła, New method for the synthesis of Al₂O₃–CaO and Al₂O₃–CaO–CaCO₃ systems from a metallic precursor by the sol–gel route, *J. Aust. Ceram. Soc.* 54 (2018) 679–690. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41779-018-0197-0>.
- [38] K.A. Salmeia, A. Neels, D. Parida, S. Lehner, D. Rentsch, S. Gaan, Insight into the Synthesis and Characterization of Organophosphorus-Based Bridged Triazine Compounds, *Molecules.* 24 (2019) 2672. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24142672>.
- [39] W. Yang, B. Tawiah, C. Yu, Y.-F. Qian, L.-L. Wang, A.C.-Y. Yuen, S.-E. Zhu, E.-Z. Hu, T.B.-Y. Chen, B. Yu, H.-D. Lu, G.H. Yeoh, X. Wang, L. Song, Y. Hu, Manufacturing, mechanical and flame retardant properties of poly(lactic acid) biocomposites based on calcium magnesium phytate and carbon nanotubes, *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 110 (2018) 227–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2018.04.027>.
- [40] M. Vassaki, C. Kotoula, P. Turhanen, D. Choquesillo-Lazarte, K.D. Demadis, Calcium and Strontium Coordination Polymers as Controlled Delivery Systems of the Anti-Osteoporosis Drug Risedronate and the Augmenting Effect of Solubilizers, *Appl. Sci.* 11 (2021) 11383. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112311383>.
- [41] W. Yuan, Z. Li, X. Xie, Z.-Y. Zhang, L. Bian, Bisphosphonate-based nanocomposite hydrogels for biomedical applications, *Bioact. Mater.* 5 (2020) 819–831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioactmat.2020.06.002>.
- [42] D.A. Ossipov, O. Gustafsson, M. Lüchow, S. El Andaloussi, M. Malkoch, Combination of Coordination and Releasable Covalent Binding for the Delivery of Antisense Therapeutics by Bisphosphonate-Hyaluronan-Oligonucleotide Conjugates, *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* 3 (2021) 2197–2210. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acspapm.1c00243>.

- [43] P. Pascaud, P. Gras, Y. Coppel, C. Rey, S. Sarda, Interaction between a Bisphosphonate, Tiludronate, and Biomimetic Nanocrystalline Apatites, *Langmuir*. 29 (2013) 2224–2232. <https://doi.org/10.1021/la3046548>.
- [44] F. Errassifi, S. Sarda, A. Barroug, A. Legrouri, H. Sfihi, C. Rey, Infrared, Raman and NMR investigations of risedronate adsorption on nanocrystalline apatites, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 420 (2014) 101–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2014.01.017>.